

Organization of painting lessons in fine arts based on modern pedagogical technology

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Abstract. Pedagogical technology is based on the "Teacher - education - student" system, in which the student becomes a subject, that is, an active participant in the educational process. In this case, the student becomes an organizer who creates conditions for his own research and observation, and a manager who controls him.

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"Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining technical and personal resources and their interaction, which has the task of making the entire teaching and learning more effective." It is possible to note the following factors that have a negative effect on the teaching of fine arts on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, that is, on its improvement: - the lack of a scientifically based system of continuous training of teachers in general educational institutions for the practical application of pedagogical technologies; - the existence of inconsistency between the current level of development of science, technology and technology and the process of ensuring the quality of professional training of visual arts teachers; - insufficient implementation of best practices in improving the process of training the professional skills of visual art teachers; - not recommending the development of lessons based on pedagogical technologies for visual arts teachers, insufficient creation of teaching-methodical complexes that allow for the organization of independent education.

Therefore, the creation of the theoretical and practical foundations of the use of pedagogical technologies in visual art classes on the basis of the effective use of the opportunities of modern educational technologies determines the relevance of the research. Level of study of the problem.

According to the documents of the Ministries of Public Education and Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the goals of modern education are not to train a narrow range of specialists for a specific field of activity, but to develop the personality of each person, pedagogy in fine arts classes. the use of technologies is its effective implementation. The use of interactive teaching methods in painting classes in fine arts is one of the current issues. The need to apply pedagogical technologies to visual art classes from interactive methods such as brainstorming, cluster, conversation, debate, discussion, puzzle, role-playing games arises based on the study and analysis of the content of pedagogical technology and the essence of traditional education.

It is well known to us that the content of traditional education is mainly built on the basis of the authoritarian position of the pedagogue in this process, the slow activity of visual art students, and the main part of the time allocated for visual art is spent on important theoretical knowledge by pedagogues. was used to describe information, it was expressed that the need to ensure the activity of students of visual arts was not felt. Until now, there has not been any more systematic scientific work or methodical-didactic manual published on the issue of pedagogical technology in teaching the science of painting in school fine art. In order to think about this issue, it would be better to start the issue a little higher and analyze the use of technology, pedagogical technology, and then the use of new pedagogical technology in the teaching of visual arts - in our opinion.

For this, first of all, it is necessary to study the lessons of visual art at school. It is known that school visual arts lessons are carried out in the form of five types of training or technology. 1. Making a picture according to the object. 2. Work on the thematic composition. 3. Decorative practical - decorative art. 4. Sculpture works. 5. Classes are conducted on the basis of art studies. Although the teaching technology of this lesson has the same content, the teaching technology in them is definitely different from each other.

That is, in the classes "drawing a picture by looking at the object itself", it is depicted from nature, that is, seeing the object itself and drawing the shape from it as much as possible. In the thematic composition, students draw a picture based on thinking, thinking, looking at the distance and remembering something. And in sculpting, the basis of the training is the technology of training with the help of physical labor, not with pencil - paint, clay - with plasticine. Bernard Shaw said, "If you try to teach a person something, he will never learn anything." In order to master the material well, the student must work on it. It is not enough to simply listen or look, and it is not possible to expect better results. The 21st century is the age of innovation.

The future of our country will be determined by the efficiency of work aimed at raising the educational system to the level of modern requirements, along with other areas of society. It is one of the modern requirements to improve the quality of creative and practical training of students, highly qualified, competitive creative specialists, artist teachers of the public education system, who operate in the conditions of the market economy, where the development of art and technology is accelerated. A horse becomes interested in science only when he consciously puts a result in the training process and is sure that he will get it. As a result of the research, the following conclusion was reached:

1. The content and ways of organizing painting classes in fine arts based on modern pedagogical technology were scientifically based.
2. Based on the study of scientific-pedagogical and methodical resources related to the topic, it was scientifically justified that the organization of classes on the basis of pedagogical technologies is an actual pedagogical problem.
3. It has been scientifically proven that the organization of painting classes in fine arts on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies is an urgent pedagogical problem.
4. The current situation and pedagogical conditions of the technologicalization of painting lessons in fine arts were studied.
5. The proposed lesson types and content of the lessons significantly increased the students' level of knowledge.

The conscious choice of students' professions based on new pedagogical technologies is important in the continuous education system in the training of competitive professionals and all-round mature personnel. The research work conducted to guide students to a conscious profession and to improve their preparation for the life process is one of the first attempts to shed light on pedagogical, psychological, methodical, and organizational possibilities. In conclusion, we can say that no matter what subject the lesson is, if we take a scientific approach, if we creatively use modern pedagogical technologies and non-traditional teaching methods in our classes, we will reach our students' goals faster.

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